

Research Article

Genetic and Phenotypic Correlations between Linear Type Traits and Milk Production Yields of Turkish Holstein Dairy Cows

*Ibrahim Tapki and Yusuf Ziya Guzey

Agriculture Faculty, Department of Animal Science, University of Mustafa Kemal, 31034 Hatay-Turkey.

ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Article No.: 072913763 DOI: 10.15580/GJAS.2013.11.072913763</p>	<p>The main objective of this study was to estimate the phenotypic and genetic correlations between 18 linear type traits and three production yields in the first lactation of Turkish Holstein dairy cows. In this study, 78 sires having at least 5 daughters and their 2721 daughters were used. Heritabilities ranged between 0.12 to 0.44. The phenotypic correlations between type traits and milk yield ranged from -0.31 to 0.29; -0.23 to 0.26 for fat yield and -0.29 to 0.25 for protein yield. Genetic correlations between linear type traits and milk yield ranged from -0.46 to 0.42; -0.41 to 0.42 for fat yield and -0.45 to 0.45 for protein yield. The high genetic correlations between angularity, udder depth, rear teat position and milk, fat and protein yields were 0.42, 0.40, 0.45; -0.46, -0.41, -0.45 and -0.46, -0.41, -0.45, respectively. In addition to high genetic correlations between these type of traits and low heritabilities recorded for rear udder height, body condition score, central ligament and locomotion traits were -0.77, 0.61, 0.65 and 0.59, respectively. The genetic correlations showed that higher yielding cows were more angular, have deeper udders, good rear teat position, high rear height, moderate body condition score, strong central ligament and long stride locomotion type traits. These results indicated that the opportunity of direct and indirect selection schemes for milk, fat and protein yields could be achievable within a national progeny-testing programme using these type traits within a selection index.</p>
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<p>*Corresponding Author Ibrahim Tapki E-mail: itapki@mku.edu.tr or ibtapki@gmail.com Phone: +90 326 245 58 45 Fax: +90 326 245 58 32</p>	
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INTRODUCTION

There is a general consensus that genetic selection towards increased milk production alone has reduced the genetic merit for health (Pryce *et al.* 1998) and fertility (Roxström *et al.* 2001; Berry *et al.* 2003) in dairy cattle. Continual deterioration in genetic merit for health and production traits internationally has led to increased diversification of selection indexes which now include more non-production, functional traits (Berry *et al.* 2004). However, the long time interval required and the poor recording of some health and production traits has led to increased interest in ancillary traits which can be more easily measured and possess a co-heritability with the traits of interest that is larger than the heritability of the individual traits of interest. Possible ancillary traits include linear type traits. Linear type traits describe biological extremes for a range of visual characteristics of an animal (Berry *et al.* 2004). At present time, 18 approved standard linear type traits are evaluated by the International Committee for Animal Recording (ICAR) using animal model procedures (Anonymous, 2010). In many countries, all dairy breed associations and many AI organizations implemented linear type trait programs that is similar to the program described by Wilson (1979). The breeding goal in dairy cattle is to increase lifetime profit per animal and unit of time. Profit is a function of production and the time that a cow remains in herd. Thus, profit can only be recorded when a cow is culled, and selection of more profitable animals should be able to be predicted by indexes from measurements at an early age of the cow (Pérez-Cabal and Alenda, 2002). Most dairy cattle breeding objectives around the world have in the past focused exclusively on production traits. At the same time, the dairy industry has seen a severe phenotypic and genetic deterioration in cow production traits, mainly due to unfavourable genetic correlations between linear type traits and milk production traits (Pryce *et al.* 2000; Kadarmideen 2004; VanRaden *et al.* 2004; Makgahlela

et al. 2007). Various studies have been conducted to quantify the importance and the impact of type traits on production traits in dairy cattle (Boldman *et al.* 1992; Pasman and Reinhardt, 1999; Larroque and Ducrocq, 2001). The aim of this study was to investigate the phenotypic and genetic correlations between linear type and milk production traits of Turkish Holstein dairy cattle population.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

This study was carried out at Ceylanpınar State and Hatay Holstein Friesian Breeders Association's Farms between October 2003 and December 2011 in Turkey. Data set was derived from 2721 Holstein primiparous cows of 40 herds and 78 sires which had at least 5 daughters. Animal were scored for 18 linear type traits plus milk, fat and protein yields (Table 1). Herds were visited for scoring, collecting data monthly during the research period. All animals were scored on a scale of 1 to 9. Each cow was scored post calving between 30 to 60 days in milk of the first lactation, just before milking time. To calculate 305-d for milk, fat and protein yields, cows were milked twice a day, a need to have two valid milk tests and 60 DIM outlined by the Delorenzo and Wiggans (1986). Since one of the assumptions of variance component estimation is normal distribution of the data within the population was tested for normality using the PROC UNIVARIATE and phenotypic correlations were estimated using the GLM procedure of the Statistical Analysis System (SAS Version 6.0, 1998). Variance and covariance components of genetic parameters were estimated Multivariate Restricted Maximum Likelihood (MTDFREML) using an animal model (Boldman *et al.*, 1995). The data consisted of 18 linear type traits and first lactation 305-day milk, fat and protein yields (Table 1). The model for data included herd, calving year, calving season and date of classification as fixed effects and calving age, classification age milking days as covariates.

Table 1: Means, standard deviations (s.d), heritabilities (h²) and standard errors (s.e) for the linear type traits and milk production traits

Type Traits	Abbreviation	SCORE		Mean	s.d.	h ²	s.e
		1	9				
Stature	STA	130 cm	150 cm>	4.09	0.97	0.39	0.08
Chest width	CW	Narrow	Wide	5.32	1.03	0.31	0.05
Body depth	BD	Shallow	Deep	5.74	1.31	0.38	0.03
Angularity	ANG	Coarse	Angular	5.18	1.05	0.32	0.06
Rump angle	RA	High pins	Low pins	3.97	1.43	0.25	0.08
Rump width	RW	Narrow	Wide	6.12	1.35	0.26	0.04
Rear legs rear view	RLRW	Toe-out	Parallel	5.15	1.03	0.22	0.06
Rear legs set	RLS	Straight	Sickled	4.50	1.16	0.20	0.06
Foot angle	FA	Low	Steep	4.06	1.11	0.16	0.05
Fore-udder attachment	FUA	Loose	Tight	4.84	1.20	0.22	0.04
Front teat position	FTP	Outside	Inside	4.78	1.19	0.44	0.08
Teat length	TL	Short	Long	5.69	1.72	0.41	0.05
Udder depth	UD	Below hock	Above hock	5.71	1.53	0.41	0.05
Rear udder height	RUH	Low	High	5.89	1.44	0.23	0.06
Central ligament	CL	Broken	Strong	5.74	1.39	0.19	0.04
Rear teat position	RTP	Wide	Close	4.37	1.21	0.36	0.06
Locomotion	LOC	Short stride	Long stride	4.52	0.93	0.12	0.07
Body condition score	BCS	Poor	Grossly fat	4.01	0.75	0.19	0.04
Milk (kg)	MILK			5772	1014	0.31	0.09
Fat (kg)	FAT			199.02	37.72	0.38	0.06
Protein (kg)	PROT			188.38	31.21	0.36	0.07

RESULTS

In addition to the abbreviations and definitions of linear type traits, Table 1 contains means, standard deviations, heritabilities and standard errors for the linear type traits and the milk, fat and protein yields. Mean milk, fat and protein yields were 5772, 199.02 and 188.38 kg respectively. Heritability estimates of linear type traits scores ranged from 0.12 to 0.44. The heritability estimates of udder type traits varied from 0.19 to 0.44 while heritability values for foot and leg traits varied from 0.12 to 0.22. The heritability estimates of milk, fat and protein yields are 0.31, 0.38 and 0.36 respectively.

Correlations of linear type traits with milk production yields

The phenotypic and genetic correlations between the linear type traits and milk production yields are given in Table 2. The phenotypic correlations between type traits

and milk yield ranged from -0.31 (udder depth and milk yield) to 0.29 (angularity and milk yield); -0.23 (udder depth and fat yield) to 0.26 (angularity and fat yield) for fat yield and -0.29 (udder depth and protein yield) to 0.25 (angularity and protein yield) for protein yield. The genetic correlations between linear type traits and milk yield ranged from -0.46 (udder depth and milk yield) to 0.42 (angularity and milk yield); -0.41 (udder depth and fat yield) to 0.42 (rear teat position and fat yield) for fat yield and -0.45 (udder depth and protein yield) to 0.45 (angularity and protein yield) for protein yield. Despite the highest positive phenotypic correlations were between angularity and milk (0.29), fat (0.26) and protein (0.25) yields, the highest negative phenotypic correlations were between udder depth and milk (-0.31), fat (-0.23) and protein (-0.29) yields. While the highest positive genetic correlations were between angularity and milk (0.42), fat (0.40) and protein (0.45) yields, the highest negative genetic correlations were between udder depth and milk (-0.46), fat (-0.41) and protein (-0.45) yields.

Table 2. Phenotypic (r_p) and genetic (r_g) correlations between the linear type traits and milk production traits

Type Traits	r_p			r_g		
	Milk (kg)	Fat (kg)	Protein (kg)	Milk (kg)	Fat (kg)	Protein (kg)
STA	0.14	0.17	0.12	0.24	0.17	0.23
CW	-0.04	-0.10	-0.10	-0.12	-0.11	-0.15
BD	0.11	0.12	0.10	0.28	0.29	0.26
ANG	0.29	0.26	0.25	0.42	0.40	0.45
RA	0.04	0.04	0.03	-0.09	-0.09	-0.13
RW	0.02	0.01	0.01	-0.03	-0.02	0.03
RLRW	0.02	0.01	0.04	0.03	0.07	0.08
RLS	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.05	0.05	0.09
FA	-0.05	-0.04	-0.02	0.02	0.03	0.08
FUA	-0.23	-0.18	-0.20	-0.27	-0.21	-0.30
FTP	-0.02	0.01	-0.02	-0.03	-0.04	0.03
TL	0.04	0.01	0.03	0.20	0.14	0.15
UD	-0.31	-0.23	-0.29	-0.46	-0.41	-0.45
RUH	0.12	0.11	0.12	0.08	0.15	0.14
CL	0.13	0.08	0.11	0.07	0.18	0.14
RTP	0.23	0.21	0.22	0.40	0.42	0.38
LOC	0.18	0.16	0.16	0.25	0.29	0.23
BCS	-0.20	-0.21	-0.19	-0.34	-0.31	-0.29

Correlations among the linear type traits

The phenotypic and genetic correlations among the linear type traits are shown in Table 3. Generally, phenotypic correlations among the linear type traits were lower than the genetic correlations. The highest negative phenotypic correlation was between body

condition score and angularity (-0.72) while positive correlation was between udder depth and fore-udder attachment (0.61). A strong negative genetic correlation existed between body condition score and angularity (-0.77) while a strong positive genetic correlation existed between udder depth and fore-udder attachment (0.76).

Table 3. Phenotypic (above diagonal) and Genetic (below diagonal) Correlations between linear type traits.

No	Traits	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18
1	STA		0.31	0.45	0.43	0.05	0.31	0.12	0.04	0.09	0.03	0.09	0.13	0.22	0.18	0.13	0.04	0.01	0.15
2	CW	0.07		0.49	0.47	0.09	0.44	0.05	0.03	0.08	0.02	-0.12	0.06	0.05	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.00	0.43
3	BD	0.45	0.50		0.09	0.28	0.47	0.13	0.15	0.03	0.07	0.02	0.13	0.02	0.01	0.05	0.02	0.03	0.05
4	ANG	0.59	-0.47	-0.01		-0.06	0.34	0.02	0.13	0.02	0.14	0.36	0.04	0.05	0.33	0.13	0.07	0.07	-0.72
5	RA	-0.18	-0.07	0.02	0.03		0.27	0.17	0.03	0.03	0.13	-0.21	0.05	0.12	0.04	0.04	-0.02	-0.02	0.01
6	RW	0.62	0.35	0.45	-0.23	0.23		0.03	0.05	0.08	0.05	0.24	0.09	0.02	0.28	0.07	0.04	-0.11	0.41
7	RLRW	0.43	0.47	-0.05	0.34	0.03	0.15		-0.52	0.49	0.37	0.01	-0.02	-0.14	0.19	0.01	-0.11	0.40	0.23
8	RLS	0.21	-0.29	-0.06	0.25	0.09	0.08	0.71		0.07	0.02	0.00	-0.02	-0.02	0.10	0.08	0.00	0.05	-0.09
9	FA	0.09	0.08	-0.10	-0.07	-0.03	0.00	0.45	-0.53		0.03	0.17	0.05	0.04	0.00	-0.07	0.00	0.00	0.04
10	FUA	0.12	0.12	-0.21	0.23	-0.23	0.52	0.49	0.41	-0.44		0.42	-0.30	0.61	-0.41	0.11	0.22	-0.02	-0.13
11	FTP	0.03	0.04	0.00	-0.08	-0.06	0.03	0.09	0.05	-0.06	0.08		-0.38	0.46	0.29	0.05	0.59	-0.18	0.03
12	TL	0.12	0.17	0.01	-0.04	-0.28	-0.31	-0.12	-0.16	0.00	-0.40	0.01		-0.21	-0.24	-0.28	0.05	0.09	-0.04
13	UD	0.30	0.21	-0.11	-0.08	0.06	0.01	0.02	0.39	0.26	0.76	0.21	-0.06		0.20	0.30	0.09	-0.11	-0.13
14	RUH	0.45	-0.32	-0.09	0.59	-0.35	0.49	0.29	0.46	-0.33	0.47	0.11	0.09	0.29		0.51	0.30	-0.05	-0.11
15	CL	0.21	-0.29	0.07	0.61	-0.46	0.01	0.26	0.38	-0.37	0.35	0.04	-0.05	0.33	0.68		0.30	0.00	-0.35
16	RTP	0.10	-0.27	0.17	0.21	0.00	0.07	0.13	0.15	-0.23	0.53	0.36	-0.45	0.10	0.59	0.67		-0.07	0.00
17	LOC	0.42	0.01	0.39	0.65	-0.44	0.29	0.48	0.06	0.37	0.00	0.15	-0.12	0.00	0.23	0.07	-0.09		0.26
18	BCS	0.01	0.61	0.36	-0.77	0.06	0.25	0.19	-0.44	0.13	0.01	-0.09	0.00	-0.42	-0.51	-0.48	0.35	-0.20	

DISCUSSION

Heritabilities of traits

All foot and leg traits had low heritability estimates in this study. While some udder traits had high heritabilities except for central ligament, fore-udder attachment and rear udder height. The other traits which related to body size had mostly intermediate heritability values. The heritability values of all foot and leg traits are similar to previously published studies (Short *et al.* 1991; Brotherstone 1994; Pérez-Cabal *et al.* 2005; Němcová *et al.* 2011) except for Mrode and Swanson, (1994), who reported heritabilities for the foot and leg traits higher than this study. The estimated heritability of the central ligament is consistent with those reported by Vollema and Groen, (1997) without Mrode and Swanson, (1994), who observed low heritability for the central ligament (0.04). The heritability of fore-udder attachment was in agreement with Weigel *et al.* (1997) except for Berry *et al.* (2004) and Dahiya (2005). For the heritability of fore-udder attachment, it was reported as 0.66 by Dahiya (2005). The estimated heritability values of rear udder height, udder depth and rear teat position were similar to Meyer *et al.* (1987), but not similar to Short *et al.* (1991), Ashraf *et al.* (2002) and Weigel *et al.* (1997). In the present study, heritabilities of teat length and rear udder height were in agreement with Mrode and Swanson (1994). The heritabilities of the rump angle, rump width, chest width, angularity and other traits which related to body size were consistent with reports by Brotherstone (1994), without Cue *et al.* (1990), DeGroot *et al.* (2002). For the body condition score, heritability is similar to Pryce *et al.* (2000). The heritability values of milk, fat and protein yields were consistent with Mrode and Swanson (1994) and Veerkamp and Brotherstone (1997), but not consistent with Miglior *et al.* (2007) and Loker *et al.* (2011).

Correlations among the traits

The high genetic correlations between angularity, udder depth, rear teat position and milk, fat and protein yields were 0.42, 0.40, 0.45; -0.46, -0.41, -0.45 and -0.46, -0.41, -0.45, respectively. In addition to high genetic correlations between these type of traits and low heritabilities recorded for rear udder height, body condition score, central ligament and locomotion traits were -0.77, 0.61, 0.65 and 0.59, respectively (Table 2). Genetic correlations between the udder and milk production traits indicate that genetic selection for increased milk productions alone will result in cows with tighter fore-udder attachment, stronger and deeper udders. Although, Brotherstone (1994) and Berry *et al.* (2004) also reported a positive genetic correlation (0.10 and 0.36) between udder support and milk yield, Brotherstone (1994) and DeGroot *et al.* (2002) reported a negative genetic correlation (-0.29 and -0.45) between fore-udder attachment and milk yield. Genetically stronger and (taller, wider and deeper) more angular cows tended to have stronger fore udder-attachments, rear udder high, central ligament and good locomotion

score. A strong genetic correlation between udder depth and fore-udder attachment (0.76); with shallow udders possessed tighter fore udder attachment. Cows with genetically stronger, shallower udders had more sickled rear legs and steeper foot angle. A strong negative genetic correlation existed between foot angle and rear legs set (-0.53) indicating that cows with a steep foot angle tended to have straighter rear legs. The phenotypic correlations among the linear type traits were similar to previously published studies (Meyer *et al.* 1987; Mrode and Swanson 1994; Berry *et al.* 2004 and Němcová *et al.* 2011). A strong negative genetic correlation existed between body condition score and angularity (-0.77) indicating that cows with more angularity had high milk, fat and protein yields. When cows had high body condition score, they had wider chest width trait. In this study, the estimated heritabilities, phenotypic and genetic correlations are different from the previously reported studies. These differences may be due to difference in models used and/or cattle population studied. There have been several heritability estimated using different data sets for recording Holstein Friesian and other dairy breeds cows in many countries for a long time; used the different linear type traits scoring methods and linear type traits scored by the different staff in various times and number of records. While in the present study all Holstein dairy cows were scored on a scale of 1 to 9. DeGroot *et al.* (2002) were scored on a 50 point scale. While Dahiya (2005) studied on local Haryana cows, Mrode and Swanson studied on Ayrshire cows.

CONCLUSIONS

The genetic correlations showed that higher yielding cows were more angular, have deeper udders, good rear teat position, high rear height, moderate body condition score, strong central ligament and long stride locomotion type traits. These results indicated that the opportunity of direct and indirect selection schemes for milk, fat and protein yields could be achievable within a national progeny-testing programme using these type traits within a selection index.

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